

FOCUS-5 Federation Atlas

Federated Data Ontology Mapping

Public Engagement Report

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2. Executive summary

This report describes the first public engagement workshop focused specifically on the development of the **Federation Atlas**, an interactive web tool designed to support clearer understanding of concepts such as federation, federated data, and federated analytics. While many glossaries, frameworks, and definitions already exist, they often remain difficult to navigate, inconsistent across settings, and poorly translated for broader audiences. The **Federation Atlas** was developed as an ontology-based resource to help make this fragmented language landscape more visible, structured, and usable for public contributors, communications professionals, researchers, and technical stakeholders.

The tool has been shaped through progressive stakeholder engagement, with input from patient and public involvement and engagement (PPIE) professionals, communications staff, the FOCUS-5 DARE UK early adopter projects, the DARE UK federated research community interest group, and DataSHIELD. Rather than functioning as a static glossary, the Atlas allows users to explore concepts through interactive graph and tabular views, with linked definitions, filters, and pathways through the material. This reflects an important principle underpinning the work: the challenge is not only to define complex terms accurately, but to communicate them in ways that are meaningful, accessible, and adaptable across different audiences and contexts.

The public workshop, held on 26 March 2026, represented the first direct public testing of the tool itself. Participants were invited through Lancashire and South Cumbria, the North West Secure Data Environment, and the Federated Research Community Interest Group. The session combined independent exploration of the tool with group discussion and real time prototyping in response to feedback. The participant group was small but demographically varied, although the EDI profile suggests stronger representation from older and retired participants than from younger groups. This is a relevant finding in itself for future engagement design.

Overall feedback on the tool was positive and encouraging. Participants clearly saw value in the work, with strong support for the ambition, interactivity, and visual mapping of relationships between concepts. The tool was widely viewed as engaging, exploratory, and more useful than a static explanatory resource. However, the dominant challenge identified was overwhelm, especially in the graph-based view. Participants did not reject the richness of the content. Rather, they felt that the current presentation asked too much of users too quickly and needed a clearer route in. This led to repeated calls for better staging, clearer entry points, stronger layering, and improved navigational support.

Several specific themes emerged from the workshop.

- First, participants wanted a more obvious starting point, such as a landing page, guided walkthrough, worked example, or “where to start” prompt.
- Second, they valued the principle of layered information and drill down, but felt it needed to be made more explicit through better labels, summaries, highlighting, and alternative ways of viewing relationships.
- Third, the session reinforced that definitions matter, but not in isolation: technically-sound wording alone is not enough if it remains difficult to understand, overly abstract, or insufficiently contextualised. Acronyms were also identified as a major accessibility barrier.
- Finally, participants highlighted the importance of offering multiple routes into the same content, including different views and potentially AI-supported navigation, to better reflect different needs, backgrounds, and cognitive styles.

General feedback on the workshop itself was also positive. The facilitation was strongly praised, and participants appreciated the effort taken to make unfamiliar material approachable. Suggestions for improvement were mainly practical: increasing attendance, allowing slightly more time, sharing review material in advance, and ensuring public input remains central throughout the whole session. These findings indicate that the approach is promising, but that both the tool and the workshop format would benefit from further refinement.

The report concludes that the **Federation Atlas** has clear potential as a public and professional resource for improving understanding of federated research concepts, but that further development is needed to improve usability, accessibility, and communicative clarity. Immediate next steps include implementing the feedback identified in this report, continuing the Federated Data Language Survey to inform early stage definition development, and strengthening collaboration with organisations such as Understanding Patient Data, PEDRI, and NHS SDE central and technical teams. Future engagement should also seek greater involvement from younger participants and continue testing how complex concepts can be communicated in ways that are both rigorous and genuinely accessible.

You can have a look at the latest version of the tool here: <https://fa-ontology-mapping.vercel.app/>

The screenshot displays the 'Language Road Map' interface for 'Federated Data & Framework Analysis'. On the left, a sidebar contains a 'Reset' button, a 'Disclaimer: Prototype Content' box, a search bar, 'Graph View' and 'Tabular View' tabs, a 'Definition Perspective' section with 'Public', 'Technical', 'Researcher', and 'Governance' buttons, and 'Framework Filters' for 'Five Safes', 'FAIR', and 'PEDRI'. The main area features a navigation bar with 'Why', 'What', 'How', and 'Who' tabs, a 'CLICK ME' button with a downward arrow, and a large green circle containing the text 'A Federation'.

3. Background

This work forms part of a wider programme involving multiple stakeholders to improve clarity and consistency in how concepts such as federation, federated data, and federated analytics are understood and communicated. The aim is to develop unified, organisationally agnostic, and generalisable definitions through whole system engagement involving public, professional, and multi-agency perspectives. There are already multiple glossaries and definitions in circulation across the TRE and SDE landscape, yet accessible resources remain limited. Previous attempts to explain concepts such as federation, federated data, federated analytics, data pooling, and eyes on or eyes off analysis have not fully landed. The issue is not necessarily a lack of content; rather, it is a lack of coherence, translation, and structure.

A central objective is to build an ontology that enables people from different backgrounds and organisations to work together with greater coherence and shared understanding. At present, terminology in this area is often inconsistent and interpreted differently across professional groups, creating challenges for both internal alignment and public communication. While different professional and organisational perspectives are necessary in implementation, a shared high-level understanding of the core characteristics of these concepts is needed to align expectations.

A scoping survey has been conducted to gather views on existing definitions and terminology, with the aim of informing the development of clearer definitions for multiple audiences including the public. Early work has made it apparent that levels of granularity need to be included to meet different audience needs as well as generalisability vs operational clarity trade-offs. This is an important precursor to the later development of more accessible public-facing definitions and supporting resources for engagement and communication. It also provides a structured way to examine concerns about language that are regularly raised across the federated research space.

4. The Federation Atlas, an interactive, publicly accessible web tool

The Federation Atlas is an interactive, publicly accessible web tool designed to support clearer understanding of the concepts, terms, and relationships that shape federated data and federated analytics. Rather than presenting definitions as a static glossary, it functions as an ontology-based resource that visually maps how key ideas connect across the wider ecosystem (Figure 1). Its purpose is both definitional precision and translation: helping public contributors, communications professionals, researchers, and technical stakeholders navigate a complex field in a more coherent and structured way. In this sense, the tool acts as both an information resource and an interpretive aid, making a fragmented language landscape more visible and more usable.

Figure 1: Graph view of the Federation Atlas.

Note the search bar, definition perspective, framework filters and definitions panel on the left side bar.

The tool has been developed through progressive stakeholder engagement, with early iterations shaped primarily by professionals working in PPIE, communications, and related system-facing roles, alongside technical input from the FOCUS-5 DARE UK early adopter project, the DARE UK federated research community interest group, and DataSHIELD. This development approach reflects the central challenge the Atlas is trying to address: not simply how to define federation accurately, but how to communicate it in ways that are accessible, meaningful, and adaptable for different audiences (Figure 2 – Tabular view alternative to graph view). Its interactive format supports exploration, layering, and multiple routes into the material, creating a foundation for future refinement through continued public testing and collaborative definition development.

Placeholder Notice: The current definitions are placeholders and for illustration only.

Language Road Map Reset

Federated Data & Framework Analysis

Disclaimer: Prototype Content

The definitions and examples provided in this prototype are AI-generated placeholders intended for illustrative purposes only. This site is a preliminary design developed to facilitate engagement with public and professional stakeholders, who will collaboratively refine and establish the final, agreed-upon content.

Search nodes, tags, definitions...

Graph View Tabular View

Definition Perspective

Public Technical Researcher Governance

Framework Filters Clear Filter

Five Safes >

FAIR >

PEDRI >

SATRE >

Details Panel

● **A Federation**

DEFINITION

PURPOSE

To enable secure collaborative research and analysis across multiple independent organizations without moving or compromising control of the underlying data.

An established network of institutions and technological systems enables researchers to query

Item	Purpose	Definition (researcher)	Essential Characteristics	SDE Example	DARE UK Example	Five Safes	FAIR	PEDRI	Ret
Federation of People <small>DEFINITION</small>	To enable individuals or groups to work together around shared goals without losing their own identity, voice, autonomy, or legal responsibility.	A federation of people is a model of human collaboration in which separate people or groups work together through agreed principles, governance, and coordination mechanisms, while remaining distinct rather than fully merging into a single unified body.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Multiple distinct people or groups: There must be more than one person, team, community, or constituency involved. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Safe People Culture of Engagement Shared purpose: The federation exists to achieve something together that matters across the whole group. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mutual Benefit 	N/A	N/A	Safe People		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mutual Benefit Effective Involvement Culture of Engagement 	• C
Federated Data <small>DEFINITION</small>	To let multiple organizations use data together in a coordinated way without requiring all the source data to be moved into one central place.	Federated data is data held across multiple independent organisations or systems that can be used in a coordinated way under shared rules, while each organisation retains stewardship and control over its own data. <small>RELATED TERMS</small> Federation = the broader collaboration model Federated data = the distributed data landscape within that model Federated analytics = analysis performed across that distributed data Federated learning = training models across distributed data without routine central pooling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data held in more than one place: The data remains distributed across multiple organisations, systems, or secure environments. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Safe Data Data Management Multiple data stewards or controllers: Different parties remain responsible for their own datasets, rather than everything being owned or governed 	N/A	N/A	Safe Data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Findable Accessible Interoperable 		• S • F
Federated Analytics <small>DEFINITION</small>		An analytical approach where you safely send your mathematical code to each hospital's dataset individually, and the software effortlessly mathematically combines the final answers for you.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analytics code executes locally at endpoints Only aggregate results transmitted back 	N/A	N/A	Safe Settings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reusable Interoperable 		• C • A • S
Research Outputs <small>DEFINITION</small>		The final scientific answers—like statistical graphs, average numbers, or trained machine learning models—that you actually take away from the secure environment to publish in your paper.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Digital Object Identifier (DOI) assigned Associated methodology published openly 	N/A	N/A	Safe Outputs		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mutual Benefit 	• S • F
Federated Storage <small>DEFINITION</small>		A setup where many different hospitals' hard drives are connected through software so you can search them all at once, even though the data is scattered everywhere.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Storage endpoints reachable via secure protocols Availability SLA > 99% 	N/A	N/A	Safe Settings			• C • C
Organizations		The established set of rules, ethics panels, and	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Legal basis for data processing established 	N/A	N/A	Safe		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Transparency 	• F

Figure 2: Tabular view of the *Federation Atlas*.

Note the search bar, definition perspective, framework filters and definitions panel on the left side bar remain the same.

5. Public engagement workshop - 26th March 2026

This workshop represents the first public engagement session focused specifically on the development of the interactive tool itself. Earlier stages have largely focused on professional sense-making, concept development, and iterative design thinking driven by the Federated Research Community Interest Group and a collective of Northern NHS SDE PPIE Professionals. This session moved the work into direct public testing, with the aim of understanding how the tool is experienced by users outside of the immediate professional community: what supports understanding, what creates overwhelm, and what changes are needed to make the resource more accessible and meaningful in practice.

The purpose of this session was not primarily to settle the fine detail of definitions. It was to explore how we develop tools and resources that make complex ideas around federated analytics more visible, accessible, and usable for different audiences. The workshop used the interactive web tool as a stimulus for discussion and feedback. The version reviewed is here: <https://fa-ontology-mapping-6z6a.vercel.app/>.

The structure of the workshop led by Dale Kirkwood (FOCUS-5) and facilitated by Jonaa Eva (DARE UK FedRes CIG) is outlined in Table 1.

Table 1: Structure of workshop activities

Duration	Activity
10 minutes	Welcome and introductions
10 minutes	Background and purpose of the session
10 minutes	Independent exploration of the tool on participants' own devices, without tutorial support, to capture genuine first impressions
30 minutes	Individual reporting back on initial experiences, observations, and suggestions
50 minutes	Open discussion, including live implementation of selected feature requests using AI enabled rapid prototyping ("vibe coding")
10 minutes	Any other business
10 minutes	Debrief between lead facilitator, facilitator, and host

5.1 Equality, Diversity and Inclusion Monitoring

Invitations to participate were shared across Lancashire and South Cumbria, the North West SDE, and the Federated Research Community Interest Group. Among the eight respondents, the participant group was predominantly middle aged to older, with most aged 45 to 54 years (n=3), followed by 55 to 64 years (n=2), 65 and over (n=2), and one respondent aged 35 to 44 years. The group was mostly female (n=5) with three male respondents, and most identified as heterosexual (n=7), with one person preferring not to say. Most participants were married (n=6), with one single and one divorced respondent. In terms of religion, Christianity was the most commonly reported faith (n=4), followed by Islam (n=2), with one respondent selecting 'other' and one preferring not to say. The sample was ethnically mixed, including White (n=3), Asian/Asian British (n=2), Black/African/Caribbean/Black British (n=1), and other ethnic group (n=1), with one participant preferring not to state their ethnicity. In relation to work status, half of respondents were retired (n=4), while the remainder included one self-employed person, one student, one unable to work, and one who preferred not to say. Three respondents reported a disability and five did not. Overall, this was a small but demographically varied group, although the profile suggests stronger representation from older and retired participants than from younger age groups (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Demographics of the public participants

6. Key findings

The overall response to the tool was encouraging; people clearly wanted to engage with it. There were several strong positive reactions, including comments such as “wow”, “fantastic effort to provide so much information in one page”, and “wonderful attempt”. The interactivity and layout were widely seen as strengths. People liked the idea of being able to click through layers and explore concepts for themselves rather than being given a static explanation.

At the same time, the clearest challenge raised across the session was overwhelm. This was not a rejection of the ambition of the tool; in many ways, it was the opposite. Participants could see the value in the richness of the content, but felt that the current presentation asks too much of the user too quickly. The message was not “there is too much here”, it was “there needs to be a better way in”.

6.1 The tool is engaging and people want to use it

The strongest positive theme was that the tool feels interactive and user-friendly. Participants liked the fact that clicking on the wheel brought up definitions and that the layout encouraged exploration. There was a sense that this was something people wanted to engage with rather than passively read.

The map itself was generally seen as a positive feature. It gave people a way to see that this is a connected landscape rather than a list of unrelated terms. There was also recognition that the work represents a serious and thoughtful attempt to make a difficult area more navigable.

6.2 Overwhelm is the main usability challenge

The most consistent challenge raised was that the tool feels overwhelming at first glance. This was especially true in the circular graph view. One participant, speaking from a neurodivergent perspective, said they found that view particularly overwhelming and preferred the tabular view. That is an important point, because it reminds us that usability is not just about aesthetics or technical functionality, but also involves cognitive accessibility and preference.

Participants recognised the wider tension here. Transparency requires information, but information provision alone is not the same thing as clarity. More information can easily lead to more complexity and confusion. What matters is getting the right information in the right format at the right point in the journey.

This is where the call for drill downs, progressive layering, and clearer levels became very important. People were not asking for the content to be removed. They were asking for it to be staged better.

Prior to engagement, the landing page had the full web of definitions (Figure 4), which, in and of itself, is not complete and illustrative. Therefore, a complete map would be even more overwhelming, though useful to convey system complexity which is hard to appreciate as a public member. A greater appreciation of the complexity may allay some frustration about delays to deliver of these more advanced data systems. As well as helping reduce delay itself by supporting better understanding internally of what is being attempted.

Figure 4 – *Federation Atlas* landing page prior to engagement – Version 1: <https://fa-ontology-mapping-6z6a.vercel.app/>

6.3 There needs to be a clearer starting point

A very strong theme was the need for a clearer entry point. Participants repeatedly asked, in effect, “where do I start?”. Suggestions included:

- a landing page,
- a “click me” or “where to start” button (Figure 5),
- a short tutorial, walkthrough or “how to use this tool” guide, and
- a worked example that narrates a user journey through the tool

Figure 5 – *Federation Atlas* landing page “vibe coded” in real-time in response to feedback during the session – Version 2: <https://fa-ontology-mapping-rh44.vercel.app/>

This reflects a broader point that the tool is not just an information resource. It can act as an operational support tool. It needs to help people orient themselves, not simply display content. Several comments suggested that better storytelling is needed within the tool itself, so that users are guided through the concepts rather than left to decode the structure on their own.

6.4 The layering is promising, but needs to be more explicit

Participants liked the principle of levels and drill downs, and some of this has already been actioned to make the levels clearer. Even so, there was a strong call for further development in this area.

The feedback suggested that people want:

- less of the full picture at first glance,
- more obvious drill downs for those who want depth,
- better labels and summaries explaining what is being viewed,
- stronger highlighting when a wheel segment is selected, and
- clearer arrows and directionality between concepts

There was also interest in alternative ways of presenting the same conceptual relationships. For example, the ontology map could potentially be presented as more of a landscape or process flow rather than only through the current circular arrangement, and/or a walk-through could be delivered via a narrated navigation.

6.5 Definitions matter, but not in isolation

A useful tension emerged around definitions. On the one hand, participants recognised that better definitions are needed and that they require further context and refinement. On the other hand, the workshop reinforced that the core problem is not simply definitional precision, but communication.

Several people felt that the current definitions panel was not yet right. There was concern that some definitions risked being patronising, while others remained too technical or insufficiently contextualised. This reflects a familiar challenge in this space. It is entirely possible to produce definitions that are technically defensible but communicatively poor.

There was a suggestion that this work should be framed in relation to PEDRI and that a public group is needed to help distill and test the definitions.

6.6 Acronyms remain a major barrier

Too many acronyms were flagged as a clear problem. Participants specifically noted acronyms such as TES and SATRE, including within filters and on the map itself. This is a fairly basic but important issue. Acronyms are often invisible to those already embedded in the field, but they are one of the quickest ways to exclude or lose people.

This also links to translation and accessibility. If we want these materials to be more easily translated, whether by humans or through digital tools, then dense acronym use will continue to undermine that goal.

6.7 People want different access routes into the same content

From an EDI perspective, an important finding was that participants valued the idea of having different routes into the tool for different audiences, rather than a single uniform experience. This points towards equity rather than equality. People do not all start from the same place, and inclusive design in this context means offering different levels, formats, and pathways while maintaining a coherent overall structure. Feedback also highlighted cognitive accessibility, with the circular graph view described by one neurodivergent participant as overwhelming, and several people noting that terminology still needed further simplification. This reinforces the need for clearer language, fewer acronyms, alternative views, and more multimodal support such as visuals, videos, worked examples, and guided navigation.

Another important theme was that there should be multiple points of access into the material. Participants raised the possibility of using AI's natural language functionality to support navigation, rather than expecting the static tool to do all the explanatory work by itself.

6.8 General workshop feedback

General feedback on the session was largely positive, with participants recognising the effort taken to introduce complex and unfamiliar concepts in an accessible way. Several respondents wanted more of this type of session, and one felt it was difficult to identify meaningful improvements because the facilitation, explanation, and structure had been handled so thoughtfully. The facilitation was praised very strongly, particularly for the facilitator's knowledge, accessibility, and ability to make difficult material approachable. Participants also felt the tool itself was promising, with some finding it easy to navigate and others describing its scope as impressive, though initially difficult to grasp.

The main suggestions for improvement were practical. These included increasing attendance, extending the session slightly to allow more time, providing review material in advance, and ensuring greater public input throughout the whole workshop rather than mainly in the first half. One respondent noted that the latter part of the meeting felt less relevant to public contributors, and another felt the tool still needs further development before it is fully effective. Overall, the feedback suggests the session was well received, but would benefit from more time, stronger pre-session preparation, and an even more consistent public-centred approach throughout.

7. Considerations and future work

Several considerations for future work emerge from both the EDI profile of participants and the workshop feedback. First, the available EDI data suggests a relative gap in engagement with younger people. This is important not only from a representational perspective, but also because younger groups may be especially valuable contributors to the development of a digital-first resource. As digital natives, they may bring different expectations about navigation, interactivity, explanation, and usability that could help strengthen the design and relevance of the tool. Future engagement activity should therefore consider more deliberate approaches to involving younger participants.

Workshop learning also suggests a number of practical improvements to the way future sessions are organised. Providing access to the tool in advance of the session would allow participants more time to explore it at their own pace and arrive better prepared to offer considered feedback. Now that a publicly

accessible demonstration version exists, this is a realistic and actionable next step. In addition, replacing the current dummy definitions with a simple placeholder statement such as “This is placeholder text” may help reduce distraction. Although participants were told that the wording of the definitions was not the main focus of the session, they were still repeatedly drawn to it, which suggests that incomplete draft content can unintentionally pull attention away from the broader aims of testing structure, navigation, and usability.

Future workshop delivery may also benefit from a clearer facilitation model. A three-person approach would likely support smoother real time testing and refinement, particularly where live prototyping is part of the method. In this model, a lead facilitator would guide discussion and participant contributions, a note taker would capture learning in a semi structured way and support the write up, and a tool developer would listen to feedback in real time and implement selected changes to further test and refine ideas. For in-person sessions in particular, this division of roles would likely improve flow and ensure that both discussion and iterative development are properly supported.

In terms of the wider programme of work, the next step should be to implement the improvements identified in the key findings of this report and continue the Federated Data Language Survey to support early stage definition development for discussion with wider stakeholder groups. There is also a strong case for exploring collaboration with Understanding Patient Data and the Patient Engagement in Data Research Initiative to support the development of public-facing definitions and examples. Alongside this, closer collaboration with NHS SDE central and technical teams would help ensure that evolving public resources are informed by technical, governance, and implementation perspectives as well as engagement expertise.

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